

**BELGIUM - FLEMISH COMMUNITY
(FLANDERS)**

Country Report on HEI types

Anna Wolfmayr and Georg Zahradnik
Updated September 2023

Belgium - Flemish Community (Flanders)

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Flanders (Belgium - Flemish Community)¹, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice², in Flanders, only institutions recognised by the Flemish government may award the degrees of Bachelor and Master. They consist of:

- officially registered institutions
- private registered institutions.

The officially registered institutions are institutions for higher education which were recognised by the authorities prior to 2004 and which can rely on government funding for their education and research activities. These institutions are listed in the Higher Education Register (<http://www.highereducation.be/home>).

It concerns the following institutions:

- University colleges (Hogeschool)
- Research universities (Universiteit)
- Institutions for post-initial education, scientific research and scientific services (not included in ETER):
- Other officially registered institutions (not included in ETER)

One special institution is the Transnational University Limburg (tUL). This university was founded under a treaty between the Netherlands and Flanders and is therefore a bi-national institution. In Flanders, it is an officially registered institution.

The private registered institutions for higher education are all the private institutions which have successfully completed a registration process and have been officially registered by the Flemish Government. The programme(s) offered by these institutions must pass the programmes test of the Accreditation Organisation of the Netherlands and Flanders (NVAO) before the institutions can register. Private registered institutions for higher education are currently not included in ETER.

¹ Belgium is a federal state with communities and regions. Education is a community matter: the Flemish Community (Flanders) is responsible for the education and training policy on the Flemish territory including education in Dutch in Brussels.

²<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/belgium-flemish-community/types-higher-education-institutions>

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 below provides a quantitative overview on the main institutional characteristics by HEI type. Universities (*Universiteit*) are all public or government-dependent institutions and have the right to award PhDs. In total, about a quarter of all Flemish HEIs included in ETER are Universities and equivalent institutions. University colleges (*Hogeschool*) account for almost three quarters of all Flemish HEIs in ETER. However, none of them awards PhDs.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private government-dependent	PhD awarding
University	Universiteit	6	3	3	6
University college	Hogeschool	16	6	10	0
Total		22	9	13	6

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of Flanders's higher education and its evolution over time.

Figure 1 shows that, despite ancient historical roots, the expansion of the system in terms of the number of HEIs is relatively recent. While the KU Leuven, the oldest Flemish university, dates back to 1425, only six other HEIs were founded before the 20th century, including five Universities (*Universiteit*) and one University College/University of Applied Science (*Hogeschool*). The figure shows two distinct patterns of expansion for Universities and University colleges with the latter one lagging behind the expansion periods of the Universities. First, while two Universities were founded in the 1970s, the first wave of expansion for University colleges only occurred in the late 1990s, increasing the number by eleven institutions. The second period of expansion started the 2000s with the opening of two more Universities followed by the foundation of four University colleges the early 2010s. Since 2014 the number of institutions has been stable.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

However, the figure above only displays organisations still independent at the end of the reporting period and does not account for mergers and other demographic events. The most recent foundation of a University in Flanders, the *Universiteit Antwerpen* in 2003, was for example the result of a merger between UFSIA (Universitaire Faculteiten Sint-Ignatius te Antwerpen), RUCA (Rijksuniversitair Centrum Antwerpen), and UIA (Universitaire Instelling Antwerpen) with the foundation of the ancestors dating back to the 1960s. Similar, the formal foundation of the latest Hogeschool, *Thomas More Mechelen-Antwerpen*, is also the result of a merger between two prior existing institutions with roots back until 1922.

Students

Figure 2 shows the number of students enrolled by level and type of HEI for the year 2020. While the total number of students is relatively balanced between Universities and University colleges, there are systematic differences between educational levels. In fact, University colleges account for over 60% of all Bachelor students but only for 4% of all Master students. As University colleges are non-PhD awarding, all PhD students are enrolled in Universities.

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Total students include ISCED 5-7

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyse the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, levels of seniority.

As shown in Figure 3, the majority of total personnel in full time equivalents (FTE), around 75%, is employed in Universities. Examining the personnel composition, this is mainly caused by the large variation in research and teaching assistants (RTAs). As only Universities are allowed to award PhDs, they are the only ones employing RTAs. Moreover, Universities have a higher share of support and administrative personnel employed, which roughly coincides with the distribution of total personnel between Universities and University colleges. In more detail, around 80% of total administrative personnel are working at Universities. Total academic personnel is divided relatively equally between the two types of HEIs, with around 52% being employed in Universities.

Figure 3. Personnel (FTE) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Since the data collection 2020, ETER also includes information on academic staff seniority level based on a classification jointly developed by OECD and EUROSTAT³. Combined with information on gender, this information allows measuring two critical issues, i.e. career prospects of academic staff and the so-called leaky pipeline, i.e. the fact that the share of female academic staff decreases systematically with seniority levels.

As of Flanders, data are available only for Universities. Ignoring other academic personnel, the majority of academic personnel is employed at the intermediate level. Regarding gender, Figure 4 shows that while seniors have a relatively unbalanced distribution of male and female workers (80% to 20%), it becomes more balanced the lower the seniority level. In fact, only 60% of personnel at the junior level is male. A similarly balanced share is found for other academic personnel.

³ OECD (2022), Education at a Glance, Paris, pp. 412-413.

Figure 4. Academic personnel by seniority level and gender (HC), 2020

Note: Unclassified personnel is not included in figure

A final important dimension is internationality since it is generally considered as beneficial for the quality of research and education. In ETER, this is measured by the share of academic personnel not having the citizenship of the country ('foreigners'). As shown by Figure 5 for the year 2020, in Universities around a quarter of academic personnel is foreign. This share has increase by around 5 percentage points over the last ten years.

Figure 5. Share of foreign academic personnel (HC) by type of HEI, 2011 and 2020

Academic personnel and financial resources

As illustrated in Figure 6, in the year 2020, Universities account for more than 70% of financial revenues and academic personnel of the whole HEI system, i.e., substantially more than their share of students. This broadly corresponds to the fact that Universities also have an important research function.

This difference is also reflected in the composition of revenues, where Universities receive a considerable proportion of revenues from (research-related) third-party funds. While state allocation remains important for all institutional types in Flanders, only for University colleges this is the dominant funding source. For Universities, third-party funding is of similar importance compared to the state allocation. Student fees play a minor role in Flanders for both Universities and University colleges.

Figure 6. Resources, academic personnel and total students enrolled by type of HEI, 2020

Figure 7. Composition of resources by type of HEI, 2020

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of the number of students, data show a relatively stable pattern with a slight increase in the number of students starting in 2016 and continuing until 2020 for both, Universities and University colleges. In terms of the number of students both Universities and University colleges have played a similarly significant role in the last ten years accounting for about half of the total students each.

Figure 8. Students enrolled by type of HEI, 2011-2020

As shown by Figure 9, the total number of academic personnel (FTE) in all HEIs increased steadily from 2011 to 2020. However, while there was a growth in the number of academic personnel (FTEs) employed in Universities between 2011 and 2020, the number reduced for University colleges by around 150 FTEs.

Figure 9. Academic personnel (FTE) by type of HEI, 2011-2020

twitter.com/eter_eu

www.eter-project.eu

eter@eter-project.eu

Università
della
Svizzera
italiana

JOANNEUM
RESEARCH
POLICIES

AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE
OF TECHNOLOGY

NIFU

Nordisk institutt for studier av
innovasjon, forskning og utdanning

SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA